

Characterization and tuning of predictive SSOD-PI controllers

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Abstract— This work proposes an event-based PI control scheme focused on FOPTD (*First Order Plus Time Delay*) processes with simple tuning methods. The scheme, called for short predictive SSOD-PI or PSSOD-PI, only considers two degree of freedom to determine the expected rate of events as well as the set-point and load disturbance rejection responses. The event-based system is characterized by defining its architecture, a stability analysis, and by providing simple ad-hoc tuning rules. Simulation results prove the effectiveness of the approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

Process control appears to be a fruitful and inspiring application field for event-based approaches. These techniques seek to achieve a satisfactory trade-off between the sources usage and the closed-loop performance [1]. It can be significantly beneficial for some constrained applications (typically in energy and bandwidth) as a way to reduce the control-loop degradation produced by network congestion [2]. A valuable example of this trade-off can be found in emerging networked control systems (NCS) [3].

In this context, last decade has been prolific in analytical results and many techniques have been proposed for the design of event-based Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers [4]. However, the design of an efficient scheme is still a challenging problem. This kind of systems not only produces nonlinear responses, but also considers more tuning parameters (the related to the controller and event conditions, respectively). Additionally, as a result of signals quantization, the inappropriate choice of tuning parameters can lead the process response to limit cycles [5]. Consequently, the configuration, tuning and synthesis of event-based controllers are problems which still remain open and challenging.

For this reason, most works proposes specific event-based control schemes and derives ad-hoc tuning rules. Particularly, it is worth mentioning the works of [1], [6]–[8]. Under this scenario, some noticeable advances have been made. There is a general consensus on the sampling algorithm, being Send-On-Delta (SOD) the commonest (see [9]–[11]). It consists in taking a new sample when a change greater than a predefined threshold Δ is detected in the signal. Additionally, one of the most extended approaches to design event-based control systems is to combine different sampling schemes in agents involved in the closed-loop. In this way, the designer can rely on the well-known automatic control theory to explain the event-based behavior [12]. Some representative approaches

based on time-event-based hybrid implementations can be consulted in [4], [12], [13].

The current work proposes an event-based PI control scheme based on the famous dead time Smith predictor as well as a set of tuning rules. For short, the strategy is called PSSOD-PI (Predictive SSOD-PI) controller. The basic idea of the SSOD-PI event-based control strategy was introduced in [14]. This approach was extended in [15], where the benefits of using the Smith predictor and the SSOD (Symmetric Send-On-Delta) sampling algorithm to design the event generator were described. Additionally, a practical tuning methodology was developed by introducing the concept of tuning regions and a set of characteristic performance indexes. In this work, a fully event-based PI controller is characterized using this methodology and ad-hoc tuning rules are derived in order to reduce the parameter space described by the tuning regions. They are evaluated using specific robustness indexes and they are compared with other well-proven tuning rules from literature.

This paper is organized as follows: in Section II, the architecture of the event-based control system is introduced. In Section III, the behavior of the system is described. A stability analysis is developed in Section IV. The tuning methodology is provided in Section V. The results from simulation are presented in Sections VI, and finally, Section VII presents the main conclusions.

Figure 1. General scheme of the event-based control system. Solid lines denote time-based signals, and dashed lines event-based signal transmission.

Figure 2. Event based control scheme including the signals and the details of the event generator.

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II. EVENT-BASED CONTROL ARCHITECTURE

The general structure of the event-based control system is shown in Figure 1. The scheme is composed of three blocks: The controller, the process plant, and the event generator. This structure represents a small variation with respect to the generic scheme introduced in [16] where the observer is integrated with the event generator. According to this approach, event-based sampling is used for the error signal and regular time-based sampling is used for the remaining signals. In this way, each time an event occurs, a new error sample is sent to the controller and its value is hold until new events are triggered.

The stability properties and the tuning methodology developed are designed by considering a FOPTD process in Figure 1 as described in the transfer function as follows:

$$P(s) = \frac{K}{\tau s + 1} e^{-Ls} \quad (1)$$

as well as a PI (Proportional-Integral) controller

$$C(s) = K_p + \frac{K_I}{s} \quad (2)$$

where K is the process gain (which is assumed to be positive without loss of generality), $\tau > 0$ is the time constant, $L \geq 0$ is the process delay, and the parameters $K_p > 0$ and $K_I > 0$ are the proportional and integral gains of the PI controller. The system is assumed to be affected by non-modeled step load disturbances $d(t)$ at the input $u(t)$ and a set-point value $r(t)$ is demanded.

The block of the event generator is detailed in Figure 2. This element characterizes the control loop as an event-based control system. Its design was proposed in [15]. It is divided into two complementary parts: a prediction unit (based on the Smith predictor structure) and a sampling unit (based on the SSOD sampling algorithm). The aim of the sampling unit is to measure and to send an error sample to the controller each time the event condition is satisfied. This task is performed using the SSOD event-based sampling algorithm, which considers two parameters: a predefined event threshold Δ and an internal state j , where $\Delta \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and $j \in \mathbb{Z}$ (see [6]).

According to this algorithm, if $e(t)$ represents the instantaneous error, and $e^*(t)$ the sampled error sent to the controller, the relationship between them is defined as an integer multiple j of the threshold Δ in the form $e^*(t) = j\Delta$.

Figure 3. Quantization relationship between $e(t)$ and $e^*(t)$.

Thus, the event-based signal $e^*(t)$ changes to the upper or lower quantization value when the time-based signal $e(t)$ increases or decreases more than the quantity of Δ with respect to the last sample as described in Figure 3 and the equation (5).

The prediction unit is defined using the scheme of the Smith predictor with the purpose of compensating the process delay in the set-point tracking task in favor of events are triggered at the required instants. Its structure is respectively composed of a model of the controller, $\bar{C}(s)$, a model of the process with delay, $\bar{P}(s)$, and another without delay, $\bar{P}_0(s)$ as follows:

$$\bar{P}_0(s) = \frac{\bar{K}}{\bar{\tau}s + 1} \quad \bar{P}(s) = \bar{P}_0(s)e^{-\bar{L}s} \quad \bar{C}(s) = C(s) \quad (3)$$

The notations \bar{K} , $\bar{\tau}$ and \bar{L} are used to consider the identified parameters that define the Smith predictor model. The emulated feedback signal called $y_r(t)$ (in advance, the feedback signal) represents the feedback signal that would have the equivalent time-based system (i.e., if the sampling unit was omitted). This signal is considered basic for understanding the events-based behavior of the proposed system and, according to Figure 3, it is calculated as the difference between the process output signal and the prediction unit output signal, namely $y(t) + \bar{y}_0(t) - \bar{y}(t)$.

III. CONTROL SYSTEM RESPONSE

First, for the sake of clarity some concepts, notations and assumptions are a priori defined:

- j : This subscript indicates the current state of the SSOD algorithm.
- t_j : Time instant in which the state j was reached (and the sample $e^*_{t_j}$ sent to the controller).
- $e^*_{t_j}$: Represents the last sample sent to the controller (at the instant t_j). Its value corresponds to $e^*_{t_j} = j\Delta$.
- T_j : Time interval between events or states. It is also defined as $T_j = T_{j \rightarrow j-1} = [t_j, t_{j-1})$, where j represents the last state reached, and $j-1$ the next (assuming that the error is decreasing).
- Without loss of generality, it is assumed that $\bar{K} = K$. Note that in processes without integrator poles the modeling errors in the steady-state gain K can be neglected.

The closed-loop response of the event-based system depends mainly on two factors: the value of the error samples and the time instants in which events occur. Note that, the feedback loop is only closed through the event generator when an event occurs. Thus, each time the instantaneous error signal described as

$$e_j(t) = r(t) - y_{r_j}(t) \quad (4)$$

exceeds a specific threshold according to (5), which defines the SSOD algorithm of the event generator, a new event is triggered and therefore, a new sample $e^*_{t_j}$ is sent to the controller.

$$e^*_j(t) = SSOD(e_j(t); \Delta) = \begin{cases} (j+1)\Delta & \text{if } e(t) \geq (j+1)\Delta \\ j\Delta & \text{if } e(t) \in [(j-1)\Delta, (j+1)\Delta] \\ (j-1)\Delta & \text{if } e(t) \leq (j-1)\Delta \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

As can be observed, the response of the instantaneous error signal essentially depends on the evolution of the feedback signal $y_r(t)$, whose response is characterized by the dynamics of the Smith predictor. In this sense, the generic expression of the feedback signal in the domain of Laplace can be obtained by analyzing the signal $y_r(t)$ under possible structured plant-model mismatches as

$$Y_{r_j}(s) = Y_{0_j}(s) + \xi_j(s) = \bar{P}_0(s)C(s)E^*_j(s) + [P(s) - \bar{P}(s)]C(s)E^*_j(s) \quad (6)$$

where $Y_{0_j}(s)$ represents the ideal part of the feedback response, which is given by the dynamics of the transfer function $\bar{P}_0(s)C(s)E^*_j(s)$, and $\xi_j(s)$ represents the extra dynamics coupled under structured modeling errors. From (6), it can be obtained the general expression of the feedback signal in the time domain as:

$$\begin{aligned} y_{r_j} &= y_{0_j}(t) + \xi_j(t) = \\ &= \alpha e^*_j(t) - \alpha e^*_j(\bar{t}) + \alpha e^*_j(\bar{t}) \\ &+ \alpha(\bar{\tau} - \tau)e^*_j(\bar{t}) \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\bar{\tau}}}\right) + y_{r_j}(t_j) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where the notation of the delay-dependent terms is simplified using the normalized expressions $\tilde{t} = t - L$ and $\bar{t} = t - \bar{L}$, and the controller parameters are defined as $K_p = \tau K_I$ and $K_I = \alpha/K$. This definition of the controller is used to simplify the tuning parameters as well as to impose a specific dynamics as explained later. The terms $y_{r_j}(t_j)$ represents the initial conditions at event instants as $y_{r_j}(t_j) = r - j\Delta$.

By analyzing (7), it can be easily demonstrated that if the equality $P(s) = \bar{P}(s)$ is satisfied, the delay produced in the system response can be compensated by the predictor and the event samples are triggered at deterministic instants such that it is satisfied that

$$y_{r_j}(t) = \alpha e^*_j(t) + y_{r_j}(t_j) \quad (8)$$

and it follows

$$y_j(t) = y_{r_j}(\bar{t}) = \alpha e^*_j(\bar{t}) + y_{r_j}(t_j) \quad (9)$$

Under this scenario, the process has the desired expected performance when using the Smith predictor (which is given by a piecewise linear response (9)), and α and Δ represents the unique design parameter of the event-based system. From the point of view of the system performance, the parameter Δ controls the distance (in magnitude) between two consecutive events and therefore the resulting number of events. The parameter α regulates how fast the response converges to the set-point value and furthermore, it is directly related to both the control effort and the capability of reducing the control error [15].

IV. PRACTICAL STABILITY FOR A FOPTD PROCESS

Practical stability of event-based systems can be ensured by demonstrating both the existence of equilibrium points as well as its reach [15]. For the sake of brevity, large demonstrations are omitted and the simplified notations are used.

It can be stated that the event-based system in Figure 1 is GUUB (Globally Uniformly Ultimately Bounded) under step input disturbance and structured uncertainty conditions if the instantaneous error reaches a band around the set-point value of $(-\Delta, \Delta)$ (typically called deadband) so that no further events occur, which can be mathematically expressed as (10)

$$\left| \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} e_0(t) \right| < \Delta \quad (10)$$

The inequality (10) is equivalent to (11).

$$|r| - \Delta < \left| \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} y_{r_0}(t_0 + t) \right| < |r| + \Delta \quad (11)$$

This means that if the final value reached by the signal $y_r(t)$ after the zero error event-based sample is triggered remains enclosed in a range $(-\Delta, \Delta)$ around the set-point, new events will not occur and, therefore, the system will have reached an equilibrium point. The expression for $y_r(t)$ in the inequality (11) can be developed according to (12)

$$\left| \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} y_{r_0}(t_0 + t) \right| = |\xi_0(t_0 + \max\{L, \bar{L}\})| \quad (12)$$

and from this, the final condition for evaluating the existence of the equilibrium point is obtained as

$$|\xi_0(t_0 + \max\{L, \bar{L}\})| < \Delta \quad (13)$$

The equation (13) denotes the evolution of the extra dynamics after the event-based sample of the zero error value is reached. To ensure process stability, the additional displacement produced inside the deadband should converge to a value lower than the upper bound of $\pm\Delta$ to avoid new events. This situation could lead the process to limit cycles or instability.

The computation of $\xi_0(t_0 + \max\{L, \bar{L}\})$ requires the computation of previous values $\xi_j(t_j + \max\{L, \bar{L}\})$ by recursive methods. For this reason, a more conservative and easily evaluable condition to guarantee the stability can be derived by computing $\xi_{jmax}(\cdot)$ given that it can be easily demonstrated that $\xi_{jmax}(\cdot) > \xi_{jmax-2}(\cdot) > \dots > \xi_2(\cdot) > \xi_1(\cdot) > \xi_0(\cdot)$. In this context, the simplest condition (and also more conservative) can be evaluated without the need of recursive algorithms, as given by (14).

$$\begin{aligned} &|\xi_{jmax-1}| = \\ &= \left| e^*_{jmax} \alpha \left[(L - \bar{L}) + \left((\tau - \bar{\tau}) \left(1 - e^{-\frac{L}{\bar{\tau}}} \right) \right) \right] \right| < \Delta \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Thus, if the condition (14) is satisfied, it can be stated that the system will have an equilibrium point in the presence of structured modeling errors and step input disturbances.

The reach of the equilibrium point can be easily demonstrated by differentiating the equation (4) including disturbances

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{e}_j(t) &= -\dot{y}_{r_j}(t) = \\
&= -e^*_{j\alpha} + e^*_{j\alpha}(\bar{t}) - e^*_{j\alpha}(\bar{t}) \\
&+ \left[e^*_{j\alpha} \left(1 - \frac{\tau}{\bar{t}} \right) + \frac{d_u K}{\tau} \right] e^{-\frac{1+\tau}{\tau}t}(\bar{t})
\end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where the terms multiplied by $e^{-\frac{1+\tau}{\tau}t}$ tends toward zero. In this way, using the final value theorem produces:

$$\dot{e}_j(t) = -\alpha e^*_{j\alpha} \quad (16)$$

demonstrating that the system tends to zero state value despite uncertainty and disturbances and that the convergence speed depends strongly on the parameter α . Therefore, if the equilibrium point exists, the event-based system will be GUUB for a given set-point r .

V. TUNING RULES

A significant result of the approach used to design the event generator is that the response of the event-based system can be predicted with reasonable precision [15]. Thus, the features of the closed loop response can be analyzed for a given set-point r by precomputing four performance indexes:

- The settling time T_{ST} .

$$T_{ST} = L + \frac{a}{|j_{max}\Delta\alpha|} + \sum_{j=|j_{max}|}^1 \frac{\Delta}{j\Delta\alpha} \quad (17)$$

where j_{max} and a represent the quotient and the remainder of the integer division $r \div \Delta$, respectively.

- The integrated absolute error IAE.

$$\begin{aligned}
IAE &= \int_0^{T_{ST}} |e(t)| dt = \\
&= |Lr| + \sum_{j=j_{max}}^1 \int_0^{T_j} \left| r - (j\Delta\alpha t + y_{r_j}(t_j)) \right| dt
\end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

- The integral absolute of the control action increment IADU (in advance control effort).

$$IADU = \int_0^{T_{ST}} \left| \frac{du(t)}{dt} \right| dt = \frac{\alpha\tau j_{max}\Delta}{K} + \sum_{j=j_{max}}^1 \left| \frac{j\Delta\alpha T_j}{K} \right| \quad (19)$$

where values T_j are:

$$T_j = \begin{cases} \frac{\Delta + a}{j\Delta\alpha} & j = j_{max} \\ \frac{1}{j\Delta\alpha} & j \in [j_{max} - 1, 1] \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

- The number of events or sampling effort S .

$$S = 2(r \div \Delta) \quad (21)$$

where the operation $r \div \Delta$ represents the integer division. The methods to obtain the indexes can be consulted in [15].

In this context, the proposed method to derive the ad-hoc tuning rules consist of optimizing the following cost function

$$J = \min_{\alpha, \Delta} [\lambda_1 \overline{T_{ST}} + \lambda_2 \overline{IAE} + \lambda_3 \overline{IADU}] \quad (22)$$

where the mentioned performance indexes have representation. A lower value of this index means that the control strategy presents a better global performance. $\overline{T_{ST}}$, \overline{IAE} , and \overline{IADU} represents the normalized values between zero and one, and the elements $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ the weighs. In particular, three tuning rules (called for short R_i) are obtained by using three different trade-offs in the sets of weights considered in the cost function:

- R_1 : With $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3$, that is, all the performance indexes has the same influence in the optimization results.
- R_2 : With $\lambda_1 = 2\lambda_2 = 2\lambda_3$, that is, the reduction of the settling time has more influence.
- R_3 : With $2\lambda_1 = 2\lambda_2 = \lambda_3$, that is, the reduction of the control effort has more influence.

From the weights considered, each tuning rule is the result of calculating the minimal value of the parameter α for many normalized FOPDT processes (namely, with $K = 1$, $\tau = 1$, and $L = 1$) with a normalized time constant $\tau \in [1, 10]$. It should be noted that the process dead time L has not a significant influence in the results of the optimization because the design of the event generator. In contrast, the parameter τ has a significant influence (in particular on the control effort index). For this reason, the tuning rules are focused on variations of the parameter τ . The sets of values for α which minimize the index J for each process can be tightly adjusted by exponentials expressions as

$$\alpha = ae^{-b\tau} + ce^{-d\tau} \quad (23)$$

which define the mentioned tuning rules R_i . The coefficients a, b, c and d can be found in Table 1. Note that the parameter Δ is also excluded from (23) for the same reason as L (its influence on J is negligible). Thus, it can be conveniently chosen to define the number of events according to (21).

With the aim of comparing the effectiveness of the tuning rules, a set of performance indexes concerning to the robustness, the set-point response, and the load disturbance rejection are introduced to evaluate the simulation results. They are summarized as follows:

- Time constant margin M_τ . This index indicates the maximum increment allowed by the identified time constant $\bar{\tau}$ by preserving the system stability, in the form $M_\tau = |\bar{\tau}/\tau|$.
- Time delay margin M_L . This indicates the maximum increment allowed by the identified dead time \bar{L} by preserving the system stability as $M_L = |\bar{L}/L|$.
- The settling time (computed from the results of the simulation) T_{st} .
- The percentage overshoot OV .
- The maximum output error e_{max} .
- The steady-state error e_{ss} .
- The number of events (computed from the results of the simulation) S_c .

TABLE I. COEFFICIENTS OF R RULES IN EQUATION (23)

	R_1	R_2	R_3
a	1.057	1.097	0.9544
b	-0.5718	-0.4555	-0.7748
c	0.7807	0.8722	0.6172
d	-0.05211	-0.04392	-0.06379

Figure 4 shows the values of the robustness indexes M_τ and M_L with respect to the normalized time constant τ/L for the five tuning rules. As can be observed, the tuning rule R_3 provides the greatest robustness indexes. The remaining rules offer similar robustness results, showing similar trends, except the AMIGO tuning rule, which provides a poor robustness. Note the good robustness of the R rules producing margins greater than 1.5 for all experiments.

In Figure 5, the values of the indexes concerning to the set-point and step input disturbance rejection responses are shown. As can be seen, the value of the settling time index increases quasi-linearly but it is not significantly affected by the parameter τ . The overshoot and the steady-state error achieved before the disturbance appears are practically zero (except in AMIGO results) and therefore they allow the system to reach the set-point value in the minimum number of events. The value of the index e_{max} is very similar for all rules evaluated. Note that this value is essentially conditioned by the process dead time. The reproduction of similar experiments with other event thresholds produces analogous behavior and trends for the studied indexes. In this context, the parameter Δ can be exclusively used to define the sampling effort, that is, the expected number of events. Complementarily, the parameter Δ can be modified in order to satisfy the stability condition (14). It can be noted that both R and SIMC rules present quite similar results for all performance indexes whereas the AMIGO tuning rule produces poor and marginal results for the event-based system. However, the R rules provide better results in comparison with SIMC for a greater range of values. It is because SIMC rules change for ratios $\tau/L > 8$.

It should be noted that the proposed evaluation has been developed considering the assumption $P(s) = \bar{P}(s)$. Next, the effectiveness of the control system and the ad-hoc tuning rules are evaluated under non-ideal conditions, namely modeling errors and disturbances.

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, simulation results are provided. In particular, the event-based control strategy and the tuning rules are evaluated using the processes considered in (23), which covers a significant range of different process dynamics within the scope of this work. In the case of P_1 , it has been assumed structured modeling errors given by variations in the range of +20% and -10% in the set of parameters (τ, L) of \bar{P}_1 , whereas the cases of P_2 and P_3 introduce unstructured modeling errors in the design. Here, models \bar{P}_2 and \bar{P}_3 were approximated to FOPTD processes using the Skogestad half rule (see [17]). The experiments in Figures 6-8 report the control system response to a set-point step change and to a unit step load disturbance. The parameter Δ was defined as a 10 % of the set-point value.

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_1 &= \frac{1}{2s+1} e^{-4s} & \bar{P}_1 &= \frac{1}{2.4s+1} e^{-3.6s} \\
 P_2 &= \frac{1}{(s+1)^4} & \bar{P}_2 &\sim \frac{1}{2.5s+1} e^{-1.5s} \\
 P_3 &= \frac{(-s+1)}{(6s+1)(2s+1)} e^{-s} & \bar{P}_3 &\sim \frac{1}{7s+1} e^{-5s}
 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Figure 4. Robustness indexes.

Figure 5. Set-point and load disturbance response indexes.

As can be observed, both the SIMC and the AMIGO tuning rules generate much more conservative controllers in comparison with the R rules. Particularly, the R rules produce more balanced controllers, which results in that the settling time and the IAE indexes are substantially improved. Additionally, the control effort derived from the R rules is not significantly greater (the controller response is a bit more oscillatory regarding the other ones) and the number of events is kept similar to the other control strategies because control error signal achieves lower bounds in the presence of disturbances. Particularly, the rule R_3 , which is the most conservative, obtains the best result in this index. Thus, the results confirm that the R rules provide better performance in the set-point and load disturbance rejection tasks of the proposed event-based control system.

It is worth stressing that the methodology used to derive the R rules could be easily employed to infer new rules by introducing different trade-off in the presented performance indexes (using different weights). In addition, other indexes could have been programmed.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This work has described an event-based control system focused on FOPTD processes which makes use of an event generator with predictive properties and a standard PI controller. A simple stability condition as well as a set of specific performance indexes can be used to evaluate the results of the transient response and the sampling technique.

Figure 6. Response of the process P_1 .

Figure 8. Response of the process P_3 .

Figure 7. Response of the process P_2 .

The approach allows the designer to use a simple methodology to derive the tuning rules. Three examples of ad-hoc tuning rules have been provided and compared with some of the most successful from literature. The control strategy has been applied to several examples with different dynamics demonstrating the effectiveness of the approach.

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